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PRODUCTION AND OPTIMIZATION OF PECTINASE BY *STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS*. ISOLATED FROM ORANGE PEEL WASTE

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ABSTRACT

A large group of pectinase enzymes cause the breakdown of pectin polysaccharides from plant tissues and form a simpler molecule known as galacturonic acid, which is also widely used to increase yields and clarity of fruit juices. In this study, two bacterial strains have been isolated from rotten fruit (orange) using serial dilutions of 10⁻² and 10⁻⁴ on 2% pectin agar media, as two bacterial strains have been identified. The pectinolytic activity was determined using pectin containing minimal essential medium and carrot waste medium (CWM). The plate assay was used to determine the temperature of 30-200C. The highest pectinolytic zone was found to be 8 mm, which was *Staphylococcus aureus*. The results indicate an efficient and promising producer of pectinase. also shows more enzyme activity, for the improvement of quality and clearance of fruit juice (Orange).

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INTRODUCTION

Fruit processing generates solid waste of up to 50% of raw materials. Generally, waste includes peels, pits, pomace, immature fruits, rejected fruits, and mechanically damaged fruits. Pectin is one of the important products recovered mainly from citrus and apple waste, Pectin is a complex branched polysaccharide that exists in the primary cell wall of plants [1]. It is a very valuable food ingredient, usually used as a gelling agent and stabilizer [11] It is usually extracted from fruits by chemical or enzymatic methods[6]. Pectin is considered to be the most complex macromolecule in nature because it can be composed of as many as 17 different monosaccharides with as many as 20 different bonds [9]. The main structural feature of pectin is linear 1, 4 α -linked D-galacturonic acid chains with different methylation degrees, which are responsible for different physiological processes[4]. The biosynthesis, function, modification, and degradation of pectin involve several key processes in the development of plants, including cell wall expansion, cell adhesion, organ formation, cell separation, and phyllodes pattern[12], In the food industry, pectin is used as jam, jelly, frozen food, and recently used as fat and/or sugar low-calorie food. In the pharmaceutical industry, it is used to reduce blood cholesterol levels and gastrointestinal diseases. Other applications of pectin include use in edible films, paper substitutes, foams, and plasticizers. In addition to the decomposition of pectin, pectin is also susceptible to thermal degradation during processing, and the degradation is affected by the nature of ions and salts present in pectin [8]. Protopectin is insoluble, so when the fruit ripens or is cooked in an acid medium, it is converted to soluble pectin. On an acidic fruit substrate, pectin is a negatively charged colloid [2]. Citrus fruit contains 0.5%–3.5% pectin which is largely present in the peel portion of the fruit [5]. As in the global world, many of the researchers work on the pectin with the different source where Oumer and Abate work on pectin producing organisms from Coffee Pulp [7]. Fruit peel wastes are used to separate pectinolytic bacterial and fungal colonies. *Bacillus sp.* and *Pseudomonas sp.* were found in the bacterial cultures, while *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, and *Penicillium chrysogenum* were found in the fungal cultures [3], Environmentally safe biotechnological methods, for which microbial enzymes are known as effective instruments, seem to be very significant in today's society [10]. The present study was aimed at isolation, characterization, and preservation of pectinase-producing bacteria from orange peel waste. The reported isolates demand additional research inputs to streamline the economical provision of pectinases to food processing units.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of samples:

For the isolation of pectinase producing bacterial strain, partially decayed Orange (*Citrus X sinensis*) Peel waste were taken from the local market Manek Chowk, Ahmedabad. Collected samples were stored at 5-10°C in freeze for further use.

Isolation and optimization of pectin degrading bacteria.

Rotten orange was used to isolate pectin degrading bacteria. Outer most part was scrapped by using sterile forceps, further serial dilutions were done with (10^{-1} to 10^{-6}) from each tube 0.2 ml of suspension were spread over on 2% pectin agar plates with modified media contain Peptone: 5.00 g/L, Meat extract B#: 1.50 g/L, Yeast extract: 1.50g/L, Sodium chloride: 5.00 g/L, Pectin: 20.00, and Agar: 15.00 g/l, plate were incubated for 24 to 48 hours at 30 \pm 2°C. after isolation further growth factor like pH (4.5, 5, and 5.5) and Temperature (25 \pm 2, 30 \pm 2, 37 \pm 2°C) incubated for 24 to 48 hours with modified media.

Morphological and biochemical Characterization of bacteria

Identification of bacterial colony were done on the basis of Macroscopic observation as (Size, Shape, Elevation, Texture, margin, Opacity, Consistency, and Pigment) Microscopic (Gram Staining), further Biochemically as Catalase test , Indole test , Methyl red-Vogas Proskauer test , Citrate test , Gelatin Hydrolysis test , Hemolysis test , Motility test , Nitrate Reduction test and Urease test were done to identify the metabolic activity.

Characterization of pectin degrading bacteria

Selected isolates were further screened for its pectinase producing ability. The selected pure isolates were again inoculated on the same 2% pectin agar media, after the incubation the plates were flooded with 2% Iodine solution and incubated for 15 min at 37°C. A clear zone indicate around colony was indicated to pectinase activity. The clear zone around the colonies were measured by ruler in mm. both the diameter of colony and clear zone was measured and Cx ratio was calculated according to the formula given by (Guangyi *et al.*, 1996).

$Cx \text{ ratio} = \frac{\text{Diameter of zone of clearance}}{\text{Diameter of Colony}}$

Preparation of Carrot waste medium (CWM)

Carrot waste medium was prepare after pre washing with d/w. HgCl₂, and Methanol, 40gm of carrot was crushed in 100ml of Distilled water in the mixer in 250 mL and flasks, mixture of flasks were further incubated on shaker at 125 rpm for 12 hours and at the same time control was kept at room temperature at static condition to check the microbial growth, 1ml of young bacterial suspension in LB broth was kept as a control, after the different interval 12, 18, 24, 48 hours the supernatant was removed from cultural broth with the help of sterile pipettes and centrifuged at 6000 rpm for 20 min. And the clear filtrate was used for determining pectinase activity.

Enzyme production

Production of enzyme was carried out by two method , which based on natural and synthetic media1) Natural Media: based on carrot waste with the composition (Carrot waste 40 gm in 100 mlDistilled water)whereas the 2) Synthetic minimal medium: Synthetic minimal medium with composition (Pectin: 5.0 gm/L , Monopotassium phosphate: 4.0 gm/L, Disodium phosphate: 6.0 gm/L, Ammonium sulphate: 2.0 gm/L, Yeast extract: 1.0 gm/L, Ferrous sulphate: 0.001 gm/L, Magnesium sulphate: 0.200 gm/L, Calcium chloride: 0.001 gm/L, Boric acid: 0.00001 gm/L, Manganese sulphate: 0.00001 gm/L, Zinc sulphate: 0.00007 gm/L, Copper sulphate: 0.00005 gm/L, Molybdenum trioxide : 0.00001 gm/L).

Enzyme assay

Enzyme was carried out by colorimetric method(Miller, 1959). The enzyme assay was based on the determination of reducing sugars produced as a result of enzymatic hydrolysis of pectin by the Dinitro salicylic acid reagent (DNSA) method. For this, 0.5 ml of 1% pectin containing sodium citrate buffer (pH 5.0) and 0.5 ml of centrifuged crude enzyme extract were added. 1.5 ml of DNS reagent was added and the test tubes were shaken to mix the contents. The test tubes were heated to boiling on the boiling water bath for 15 min. Then these were cooled and 8 ml of distilled water was added to the contents of each tube and the absorbance was measured at 540 nm using Spectrophotometer. The enzyme and substrate blanks were run parallel. The standard curve was prepared for reducing sugars with galactose. One enzyme unit of polygalacturonase is the number of μM of reducing sugars measured in terms of galactose, produced as a result of the action of 0.5 ml of enzyme extract in 1 minute at $35\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$.The enzyme activity was expressed in Enzyme Unit (μ) per millilitre (μ/ml).

$$\text{Laccase Activity (U/ml)} = \frac{\text{Absorbance} * \text{Total assay volume (ml)} * 10^6}{\text{Time (min)} * \text{enzyme volume (ml)} * \epsilon}$$

Application of crude pectinase in juice extraction and clarification

Fruit juices is turbid and cloudy after their extraction from the pulp. For the clarification of juices, industrial level enzymes were used., pectinase enzyme is very common for the clearance of juices. It is extracted from a pectin minimal medium called a crude enzyme (3 days, 125 rpm, $30\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$). Then 20mL of this crude pectinase enzyme was added to the unqualified juice of orange in a 250 ml flask. The flasks containing the enzyme and the juice were kept for 2 days at 125 rpm. The flasks were then kept in the water bath for 1 hour at $90 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. The juice was then filtered using Whatman filter paper. This juice was then checked for its viscosity by Ostwald's viscometer. The control was also kept which contained no enzyme.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the present study we carried out the pectin degrading organisms from fruit peel from orange, where during primary observation Total two bacterial isolates were obtained during isolation on 2%pectin agar plate and they were named Ora1, Ora2 (Isolates from orange). microscopic and macroscopic observation where the result as follows:

Figure 1 : Gram staining result Ora-1 and Ora-2.

Table 1 Gram staining characteristic result.

Isolates	Ora 1	Ora 2
Size	Small	Intermediate
Shape	Round	Round
Elevation	Convex	Slightly raised
Texture	Smooth	Smooth
Margin	Entire	Entire
Opacity	Opaque	Translucent
Consistency	Gel Like	Moist
Pigment	Staphyloxanthin (Yellow)	Nil
Gram's reaction	Gram Positive Coccus	Gram Negative short rods

Characterization of pectin degrading bacteria

Isolates were screen to check the efficiently of isolates among them, one isolates showing a translucent clear zone around the colony with addition of 2% iodine solution and it consideration for further process. the cx ratios were calculated as the formula given below:

Figure 2 Plate showing pectin degrading zones by addition of 2% iodine.

Table 2 Cx ratio of the isolates.

Isolates	Diameter of zone (mm)	Diameter of colony (mm)	Cx Ratio
Ora 1	8	5	1.6

Biochemical Analysis

In the Biochemical analysis majority of test are represent the +Ve result which include Catalase test, Indole test, MR test, VP test, Citrate test, Gelatine Hydrolysis, Hemolysis, Motility test, Nitrate reduction and Urease test where in case of Indole test it represent the -Ve Result. According to the biochemical it determines that the "Ora 1" isolate, which represent as Gram positive coccus as *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Table 3 Biochemical analysis of Ora-1 Isolates.

Isolates	Ora-1
Catalase test	+Ve
Indole test	-Ve
MR test	+Ve
VP test	+Ve
Citrate test	+Ve
Gelatine Hydrolysis	+Ve
Hemolysis	+Ve
Motility test	+Ve
Nitrate reduction	+Ve
Urease test	+Ve

Figure 3 BPA media, grey coloured colonies, which giving confirmation that the “Ora 1” isolate is *Staphylococcus aureus* Enzyme activity in Carrot waste medium (CWM).

Figure 4 [A] = Control (without inoculums) and [B] = Inoculated flasks with isolate after 48 hours.

Most of the Enzymes are affected by changes in pH. The most favorable pH valuepoint where the enzyme is most active. Carrot waste medium is natural source of determine production of pectinase enzyme by the giving favorable pH value (5). After the inoculums we observe the quality of enzyme production with different time interval which recorded in table.

Table 4 Enzyme activity (μ /ml) in Carrot waste medium.

Hours	“Ora 1”
12	4.18
18	6.86
24	7.35
48	8.22

Figure 5 Enzyme activity in μ /mL of the isolate from carrot waste medium.

The isolate ‘Ora 1’ (*Staphylococcus aureus*) exhibited enzymatic potential when tested for pectinase after 48 hours. The result indicates the increase in the enzyme activity with respect to the time interval where the highest amount production is recorded at 48hrs with 8.22 μ /ml as with respect to 24 (7.35 μ /ml), 18 (6.86 μ /ml) and 12 (4.18 μ /ml).

Enzyme activity in Minimal essential medium (MEM)

Figure 6 : [C]= control (Without inoculate and [D]= Inoculated flask with isolate 48 hours.

Time	“Ora 1”
12	4.38
18	5.94
24	7.06
48	9.49

Figure 7 Enzyme activity (μ /ml) in Minimal essential medium.

Figure 8 Enzyme activity (μ /ml) in Minimal essential medium based on time.

This Above graph represent the production of enzymes with minimal essential media whet as after 24 hrs the production of enzymes were expanded to other time interval, the highest production is 9.49 μ /ml at 48 hrs , where as other activity as follows 24(7.06 μ /ml), 18 (5.94 μ /ml), and in 12 (4.38 μ /ml) ,The Comparative production of enzyme from Carrot waste medium and minimal essential media were represented as graphically representation.

Comparative study

Figure 9 Comparative production of Both Media CWM and MEM.

This graph shows the production of the enzyme in two different media one in natural and another is synthetic media, as the production of enzymes consent the highest amount of production is observe highest at 48 hrs where CWM- 8.22 and MSM-9.49 where the difference between both the media is less deferrer the difference is 1.22 μ /ml, wherein case of 24 hrs and 18 hrs Enzyme is observed higher in carrot waste medium compare to minimal essential media and in case of 12 hrs the same MSM observes the highest concerning CWM.

Application: Juice clarification

Pectinase enzyme was applied for the clarification of orange juice and the results observed are as below

Table 5 Viscosity measurement of fruit juice by Ostwald’s viscometer

Flask	Orange juice time(sec)
Control	4.4
Crude Pectinase	3.8

Figure 10 Enzyme treatment of the orange juice.

This method is applied to check the activity of enzymes in Fruit juices that are turbid and cloudy after their extraction from the pulp. For the clarification of juices, enzymes were used at the industrial level. The use of the pectinase enzyme is very common for the clearance of juices., after the completion of the entire method of pectin degradation it represented as a clearance of juice, after 2 days, Pectinases are used for the clarification of the juice by breaking the polysaccharide pectin structure present in the cell wall of plants into galacturonic acid monomers. Pectin structure breakage facilitates the filtration process and increases the total yield of juice.

CONCLUSION

Total two bacterial isolates were isolated from decayed fruit (Orange) using PAM (2% Pectin Agar Medium). From the microscopic observation, it observes that both isolates were showing the different gram reactions where Gram-positive cocci and Gram-negative short rod. Which coded as Ora 1 and Ora 2. In the primary screening of pectin producing organism, Ora-1 rise the potential result show the positive result, based on the biochemical analysis it recorded as *Staphylococcus aureus*, here we check the production of enzyme activity with two different media Orange Waste Medium and minimal essential media in both the media it 48 hrs production shows the higher production and extracted crude enzyme can be used for the clarification of fruit juice. And the clear juice was obtained when it was treated with the crude enzyme. as efficient pectinase producing bacterial strain that can be used for various industrial applications.

REFERENCES

1. Bonnin, E., Garnier, C., & Ralet, M. C. (2014). Pectin-modifying enzymes and pectin-derived materials: applications and impacts. *Applied microbiology and biotechnology*, 98(2), 519-532.
2. Caballero, B., Trugo, L. C., & Finglas, P. M. (2003). *Encyclopedia of food sciences and nutrition*. Academic.
3. Geetha, M., Saranraj, P., Mahalakshmi, S., & Reetha, D. (2012). Screening of pectinase producing bacteria and fungi for its pectinolytic activity using fruit wastes. *Int J Biochem Biotech Sci*, 1, 30-42.
4. Knox, J. P. (2002). Cell and developmental biology of pectins. *Pectins and their manipulation*.
5. Mudgil, D. (2017). The interaction between insoluble and soluble fiber. In *Dietary fiber for the prevention of cardiovascular disease* (pp. 35-59). Academic Press.
6. Munarin, F. A. B. I. O. L. A., Tanzi, M. C., & Petrini, P. A. O. L. A. (2012). Advances in biomedical applications of pectin gels. *International journal of biological macromolecules*, 51(4), 681-689.
7. Oumer, O. J., & Abate, D. (2018). Screening and molecular identification of pectinase producing microbes from coffee pulp. *BioMed research international*, 2018.
8. Thakur, B. R., Singh, R. K., Handa, A. K., & Rao, M. A. (1997). Chemistry and uses of pectin—a review. *Critical Reviews in Food Science & Nutrition*, 37(1), 47-73.
9. Voragen, A. G., Coenen, G. J., Verhoef, R. P., & Schols, H. A. (2009). Pectin, a versatile polysaccharide present in plant cell walls. *Structural Chemistry*, 20(2), 263-275.
10. Vuppu, S., & Mishra, M. (2011). An Overview of Some Reported Soil Enzyme Producing Microorganisms. *Indian Journal of Fundamental and Applied Life Sciences*, 1(4), 180-86.
11. Willats, W. G., Knox, J. P., & Mikkelsen, J. D. (2006). Pectin: new insights into an old polymer are starting to gel. *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, 17(3), 97-104.
12. Wolf, S., Mouille, G., & Pelloux, J. (2009). Homogalacturonan methyl-esterification and plant development. *Molecular plant*, 2(5), 851-860.

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